

CAPABLE

Cancer Patients Better Life Experience

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Final platform version and deployment on all the clinical sites involved

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DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos etc.	
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PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential (Consortium members including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified Information (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	

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1. Version history

Version	Date	Author	Comments
1.0	15/1/2023	Matteo Gabetta (BIOM)	
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2. Executive summary

The aim of this deliverable is to provide context for the CAPABLE system demonstration video which is available at [this link](#). A brief description about the scope of the demonstration is followed by a detailed description of the scenario that will be used during the demo.

The demonstration video was recorded in early 2023; the demo will also be shown during the consortium meeting that will happen on January 31st and February 1st, 2023.

Given the decoupled nature of the CAPABLE architecture, the efforts that led to the completion of this demo were twofold: on the one hand, each involved partner carried out the development of the component under their own responsibility, on the other hand there was a global effort to make the different components communicate with each other. All these efforts have been coordinated by Task Force 1, focused on the development of the final CAPABLE architecture.

3. Scope of the demo

The demonstration involves most of the components of the CAPABLE architecture described in Figure 1 and covers many interactions between them; in particular, the included components are:

- Data Platform (DP), storing and providing patient-level data through an HL7 FHIR interface;
- Case Manager (CM), managing events related to Data Platform and providing notifications to other components;
- Knowledge-Data Ontology Mapper (KDOM), computing abstractions from raw data stored in the DP;
- Deontics Engine, executing computer-interpretable clinical practice guidelines (CIGs) defined using the PROforma language;
- GoCom Multimorbidity controller, checking for possible adverse interactions between clinical tasks recommended for multimorbid patients and resolving them;
- Physician DSS, providing guideline-based decision support for clinicians when managing cancer patients;
- Virtual Coach (VC), providing coaching support combining clinical (guideline-based) and non-clinical recommendations to cancer patients staying at home;
- Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs), Patient App on the smartphone and Physician App on the Web, managing all interactions of the users of the CAPABLE system.

The Deontics Engine is used by both Physician DSS and Virtual Coach (more precisely, they use different instances of the Engine). Moreover, GoCom queries the Deontics Engine when checking for possible adverse interactions between tasks to get detailed characteristics of CIG tasks. Interactions between the Deontics Engine and other components are handled through a web-based (REST) API. GoCom is invoked by Physician DSS and Virtual Coach -- in such case communication employs Data Platform and Case Manager.

All components have been effectively deployed in the premises made available by the partners responsible for their development; thus, all the interactions between these components that are shown in the demo are happening live.

For the first time in WP4 deliverables, the GUIs are effectively involved in the demonstration, thus including one of the most important and certainly the most critical component in terms of the user interaction and experience.

For the demonstration's sake, data integration procedures (Extract, Transform, Load, ETL) between a hospital system (electronic health record, EHR) and CAPABLE have been excluded because they depend on the specific setting (i.e., the two hospital sites where the CAPABLE system is installed), they are not part of the *live* system and are activated only once per day bringing in data from the EHR. Moreover, also the sensor module, responsible of importing patient data generated through wearable devices into the system, is not part of the presentation since raw data need to be pre-processed at the vendor cloud before becoming available for import into the CAPABLE system.

Original goal of this deliverable was to run the demonstration at the two clinical sites involved in the project; despite the process of deploying the CAPABLE components at the hospitals is at an advanced stage and is expected to be completed in weeks, it wasn't already possible to demonstrate the system there. Below is the most up to date status update from the sites:

- NKI (Amsterdam): all partners responsible of specific components can access the hospital premises through VPN connection; most of the CAPABLE components have been installed there and preliminary access to the clinical systems has been established;
- ICSM (Pavia): virtual machines for each component have been ordered and will be delivered soon; access to clinical system is on the way.

Figure 1. The CAPABLE overall architecture.

4. Scenario

The demo, designed together with clinicians and patients' association involved in the project, focuses on the management of the diarrhea adverse event. In CAPABLE, the guideline for diarrhea treatment has been formalized by harmonizing knowledge contained in the two ESMO guidelines "Diarrhea in adult cancer patients: ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines" [2] and "Management of toxicities from immunotherapy: ESMO Clinical Practice Guideline for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up" [3].

The demo revolves around a patient fictionally named John Smith.

John is 67 years old, and he is affected by renal cancer; apart from his main diagnosis, John has no significant clinical history. The demo follows John during a period spanning over 4 days, starting from the enrollment visit (day 0) were, on the one hand, patient starts using the CAPABLE smartphone application and completes his first questionnaire to define his profile and, on the other hand, the clinician inserts relevant clinical data, and prescribes oncological and support therapies associated to the patient.

After two days (day 2) John begins to experience the side effects of cancer therapy and reports the symptom of diarrhea. Following the ESMO guideline dedicated to diarrhea implemented in CAPABLE, the system supports the management of the adverse effect by sending pharmacological suggestions to the clinician and by sending tips to the patient until the symptom ends.

The scenario is divided in 5 segments, executed in sequence, and verified by the CAPABLE simulator. In the following paragraphs each segment will be briefly introduced.

4.1. Segment 1 – Day 0 - Enrollment

- Physician, through Physician App, enrolls John Smith
- The patient starts using the CAPABLE Patient App running on a smartphone
- The patient completes the first CAPABLE questionnaire

4.2. Segment 2 - Day 0 - Treatment prescription

- Physician prescribes Sunitinib as cancer treatment
- Physician prescribes Loperamide (as needed), a drug used to treat diarrhea, that is a frequent adverse event related to Sunitinib
- The patient, through the Patient App, reports taking Sunitinib

4.3. Segment 3 - Day 2 - Symptom reporting

- The patient reports diarrhea (CTCAE level 2)
- Virtual Coach sends self-care instructions and contact information (the patient is suggested to contact the oncological team) and asks for other symptoms related to diarrhea
- Taking Loperamide is recommended to the patient (since it was prescribed "as needed" by the oncologist)
- The patient, through the Patient App, performs the Breathing Exercise *virtual capsule* (one of the non-pharmacological interventions that could improve the patient's well-being)

4.4. Segment 4 – Day 3 - Symptom update

- Virtual Coach asks the patient for diarrhea update
- The patient reports diarrhea update (CTCAE level 1)
- Virtual Coach sends contact information (the patient is suggested to monitor the symptom; no more need, at the moment, to contact the oncological team)
- Taking Loperamide is recommended to the patient again
- Physician receives recommendations related to diarrhea management from the Physician DSS

4.5. Segment 5 – Day 4 - Symptom update

- Virtual Coach asks the patient for diarrhea update
- The patient reports that the symptom is gone (absent)
- Virtual Coach informs the patient that he can share his experience about the diarrhea episode in the dedicated AIMAC (the patients association) forum
- The patient goes for a walk and, through the Patient App, he reports having performed the *My Usual Walk* capsule

5. Summary

This document describes CAPABLE Platform final iteration demonstration (M36). Since the 3rd iteration [4], the platform has undergone the following upgrades:

- All components are now ready to be deployed at the two clinical sites involved in the project.
- GUIs (Physician and Patient Apps) are now effectively integrated in the system and provide users with the means to take advantage of CAPABLE functionalities.

In few weeks both NKI and ICSM sites are expected to obtain the complete and working CAPABLE architecture to support the clinical study.

6. References

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- [3] Haanen J, Obeid M, Spain L, Carbonnel F, Wang Y, Robert C, Lyon AR, Wick W, Kostine M, Peters S, Jordan K, Larkin J; ESMO Guidelines Committee. Management of toxicities from immunotherapy: ESMO Clinical Practice Guideline for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up. *Ann Oncol.* 2022 Dec;33(12):1217-1238.
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